

[Biomarker Analytical Laboratories](#)

RECETOX, Faculty of Science, Masaryk University,
Czech Republic

**Title: SOP for GC Thermo Trace 1310 - ISQ 7000 –
Advanced custom tuning and calibration instructions**

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Authors: Hana Seličová

Summary

This section describes the advanced settings of custom Tuning and checking the Calibration for GC ISQ 7000.

IMPORTANT

Always make a note about positive/negative calibration and tune the MS to the Logbook on the desktop of the ISQ computer.

Always set the oven temperature for lower values (depends on the column – in DB-Sil5 columns for 80 °C, for more sensitive columns like WAX 40 °C). In lower temperatures the column has lower background, thus the tuning is done on “cleaner” settings. The optimal temperatures of the Ion Source and Transfer Line are 250 °C for both.

Tuning of the single quadrupole MS (ISQ MS)

1. Set the oven temperature to standby temperature for the specific column.

NOTE: This temperature differs between column types.

- DB-Sil5 columns = up to 80 °C
- more sensitive columns like WAX = approximately 40 °C.

2. Open the ISQ 7000 Dashboard (Figure 1).

3. Choose the Air & Water / Tune (Figure 1).

Figure 1 - Air and Water / Tune in ISQ 7000 Dashboard

4. Check the Air and Water present in the spectra (explained in detail in the [“SOP for GC ISQ 7000 Single Quadrupole Mass Spectrometer - Turning on, calibration, tuning, and shutting down the system”](#)).
5. Check the intensity of the noise in the spectra: Spectra → Full (Figure 2) and remember or write down the Peak intensity – this is the intensity of your Noise.

Figure 2 - Full scan spectrum

6. Cal. Gas level → EI
7. Check the intensity of the calibration masses signals in the spectra and their ratios, remember or write down the Peak intensity – this is the intensity of your Signal.
8. **Check if the Signal is at least 1,5x of magnitude higher than the Noise** (in optimal case 2x of the magnitude of the Noise).
9. The specific masses could be checked extra: Spectra → 5 (Figure 3)

Figure 3 - Check for the calibration masses (Spectra 5)

NOTE: Higher masses always have slightly worse resolution.

NOTE: The masses can be changed depending on the masses of the analytes we want to observe in our analysis (Figure 3). Each of the tabs can have different mass, those on the Figure are only default. The width of the peak could be also changed.

NOTE: Each of the masses have different % of abundancy in the relative spectra (Table 1). We can check the intensity of those masses using the table of calibration masses of calibration gas (PTFBA): e.g. if the mass 68,9 have the ratio 100 and the 130,9 have the 36,31, the expected intensity of the 130,9 will be 1/3 of the 68,9. The ions can be also checked via comparison – if two masses has similar ratio, they should have also similar intensity (e.g.

313,9 and 375,9 have both ratio around 0,35 so their intensities should be in the same order of magnitude and very similar).

Table 1 - EI PFTBA Calibration gas ratios

PFTBA			
m/z	ratio	m/z	ratio
49.99680	0.73	225.99030	0.56
68.99518	100.00	230.98560	0.47
92.99518	0.56	263.98705	8.38
99.99358	6.31	313.98386	0.32
113.99669	2.34	325.98386	0.16
118.99199	7.80	375.98067	0.38
130.99199	36.31	413.97748	1.64
149.99039	1.29	425.97748	0.85
163.99350	0.56	463.97429	1.02
168.98877	3.24	501.97110	1.90
175.99350	0.91	537.97112	0.13
180.98877	1.31	575.96796	0.32
213.99030	0.76	613.96471	0.64
218.98560	38.07		

NOTE: Mentioned Table 1 is for HRMS, this is LRMS – the orders of magnitudes of m/z intensities should be still the same, the ratio may slightly differ.

10. If the water / air ratios and calibration masses are **OK**, the tuning can be done.

When to Tune what and how

NOTE: To determine which Tune is needed to be done,

check the [“SOP for GC ISQ 7000 Single Quadrupole Mass](#)

[Spectrometer - Turning on, calibration, tuning, and shutting down the system”](#), where is the Figure 4 from or check the official User Manual for the instrument, where is this described in more detail).

Ion source exchange:

- Only Lenses and Repeller Voltage need to be Tuned → Customized Tuning **or** EI Tune

Column exchange:

- Only Leak Check performed → Customized Tuning **or** EI Check

The full maintenance of the machine:

- Full Tune **or** Initial Tune

Figure 4 - Tune Types and their usage

Customized tune settings creation

NOTE: This is the only place, where the mass calibration could be proceeded in ISQ 7000.

Opposed to the Exactives, this instrument does not have specific tab for Calibration. Both Tuning and Calibration is done via AutoTune.

- a. ISQ Dashboard → AutoTune → Tune Types → choose desired tune that you want to modify (in this case EI Check) → Copy (Figure 5).

Figure 5 - Creation of the custom tune file - Part 1

- b. Find the copy in the Tune types → Edit (Figure 6).

Figure 6 - Creation of the custom tune file - Part 2

- c. Change the settings as you need to have them (here example of the Check file for daily checks of the basic parameters WITHOUT performing calibration).
- d. Go tab by tab and change the settings. The more detailed description of all of the tabs could be found at the end of this document.

NOTE: In General (Figure 7) you need to have on the step 2 – Show advanced settings, otherwise you will not be allowed to do any of other steps.

Figure 7 - Settings of the parameters in Custom Tune - Part 1

NOTE: You need only to check the calibration, not to perform it. This is only for checking the machine. Tuning is done in different Tune sets by allowing the “Perform mass calibration” check.

NOTE: The settings of the Ion source (Figure 8) need to be set on **CUSTOM every time**, because if it won't, the instrument will just tune it anyhow for the instrument to have high intensities of the peaks and calibrant. Those parameters are set based on the group consensus based on the machine parameters. Selected values for optimal parameters are shown at Figure 8.

Figure 8 - Settings of the parameters in Custom Tune - Part 2

NOTE: Those parameters (Figure 8) are very important to normalize the checks of the instruments to standard set of values. If the parameters are changed by the instrument to

achieve optimal responses, the checking of the instrument is not done with the same conditions.

NOTE: The most important tab in this Check is the Diagnostics tab (Figure 9), where the checking of separate parts of instrument can be set. Exceptionally important are Detector, Filament and Leak check. Other are not so needed.

NOTE: On the Detector tab (Figure 9), everything must be off, so the machine is not trying to adjust or tune the detector.

NOTE: Report tab (Figure 9) is saying what will appear in the Tune Report that is generated after every tuning or checking. The SIM masses need to be chosen based on the analysis, that is currently on – e.g. if my analysis is mainly around 200-300 amu, I would need to see mainly masses at 219 and 264.

Figure 9 - Settings of the parameters in Custom Tune - Part 3

e. Once the Tuning is done → **Save** and you have your Custom Tune setting ready to use.

1. AutoTune → “EI Check updated” (select your custom tuning file and let it run) →

Start.

NOTE: If you enable the “Show spectra” tab, you can observe the tuning process better by watching the peak shapes.

2. ISQ Dashboard → View Tune Report

NOTE: For the machine to be ready to use, all the checks set need to be in “Pass” state (Figure 10).

Filament Check	Pass	VS	Filament Check	Fail. Filament 1: Filament leakage current readback is out of tolerance. Filament 2: Filament leakage current readback is out of tolerance.
Lens Check	not performed		Lens Check	not performed
Leak Check	Pass		Leak Check	Pass
Power Supply Check	not performed		Power Supply Check	not performed
RFDC Check	not performed		RFDC Check	not performed
Temperature Check	not performed		Temperature Check	not performed
Detector Check	Pass		Detector Check	Fail. Dynode readback in negative i/n mode is out of tolerance.
Vacuum Check	not performed		Vacuum Check	not performed
Communication Check	not performed		Communication Check	not performed
Ion Guide Frequency Check	not performed		Ion Guide Frequency Check	not performed
Q1 Frequency Check	not performed	Q1 Frequency Check	not performed	

Figure 10 - Passing and failing the controls

NOTE: Filament and detector check are tightly connected – if one of them fails, there is high probability the second will too and in most cases the problem is burned filament.

NOTEs on the Tabs in Tune:

- General:
 - Selecting the mass calibration – performed / checked only
 - Changing the settings for the saving and further work with the Files – which tune it uses for this Tuning (recommended to keep it on Last Saved for being up to date).
- Ion Source:
 - Emission current, Electron energy, Electron positive and negative voltage could all be taken from the Tune file (this depends on the settings in General on which Tune file) or it can be customized for specific amounts.
- Targets:
 - Recommended to keep it off, then it would keep it on the ratios that are in the PFTBA table for HRMS (Could be found in “SOP for GC 1310 Thermo Trace ISQ 7000 - Daily maintenance and Checking of the system”). If it is on, we can adjust the ratios of the masses. Really advanced settings. If you are not 100 % certain, rather don’t change.
- Detector:

- The initial detector gain is recommended to be 3×10^5
→ the instrument will take this as the default level for the detector gain
- The higher the Detector Gain, the higher also the intensities – but also of the noise as it will catch everything – so the lower the Detector Gain is in general better.

TROUBLESHOOTING: The detector gain is tightly connected with Electron multiplier – in case that the Report shows high Multiplier voltage (over 2400 V it is already worse, but the limit is 3000 V), the Dec. Gain will be also higher → then it is needed to exchange the Multiplier (call the service technician, not user maintenance!)

- Tune detector **or** Adjust detector sensitivity could be selected – not both together as the detector would be trying to adjust the sensitivity while tuning.
- Adjusting detector sensitivity is done on the mass we need the method to be the most sensitive – e.g. if all the analytes are in the range of 100-140, we would choose the mass 131 etc.
- Diagnostics:
 - Select the required parameters here – for Daily checking of the system Detector check, Filament Check and Leak check are needed.
 - For Tuning only of the ion source, the Lenses and Leak check are the only parameters required.
- Report:
 - SIM masses could be selected here – it would be the most sensitive around those masses, so if you are not having masses around 500 in the expected results, you do not need to have it there. Adjust based of the expected ions of the analyte.
- Lenses:
 - The higher masses could be deleted simply by Delete button on your computer, the Lenses do not need to be tuned on those, if you are not using them at all. They won't be deleted automatically.
- Resolution:
 - Can be off,
 - If you wish to have them on, the m/z resolutions could be changed accordingly to your analysis.